

ChildTinyTalks (CTT): A Benchmark Dataset and Baseline for Expressive Child Speech Synthesis

Shaimaa Alwaisi, Mohammed Salah Al-Radhi, and Géza Németh

Department of Telecommunication and Artificial intelligence
Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Budapest, Hungary

shaima.alwaisi@edu.bme.hu, {malradhi,nemeth}@tmit.bme.hu

Abstract. Designing expressive speech synthesis for child voice remains an unresolved problem. One of the major dilemmas faced by child TTS systems and child speech synthesis is the scarcity of datasets to train opaque data-hungry DNN-based models. Only a few datasets were proposed for the purpose of building child conversational AI agents, and many of them come with challenges such as noisy data and indiscernible speech. With this in mind, we introduce the Child-TinyTalks (CTT) dataset, comprising 2 hours of speech collected from 25 kids in grades ranging from third to fourth grade, who are telling stories and sharing their experiences. The new dataset containing 1200 audio samples has been transcribed at the word level, comprising 4 classes of voice expressions. To verify the effectiveness of CTT in real-world situations, AutoVocoder models were trained and synthesized samples were generated. The models were trained on both the LJSpeech large scale dataset and our CTT dataset. Initial experimental results indicate that the CTT dataset can steadily give comparable results with acoustic model trained on a large-scale dataset with a size of less than 10% of the large dataset.

Keywords: child speech dataset, child speech, AutoVocoder.

1 Introduction

Despite the success stories in expressive Text-To-Speech TTS and speech synthesis models for adults [1], [2], [3], designing fully expressive TTS for children remains a challenge. One of the primary factors contributing to these successes is the use of high-quality benchmark datasets and low rate of errors in scientific challenges [4], [5]. Nevertheless, the limited availability of suitable training child datasets has hampered the development of TTS and Expressive TTS systems for children. However, it is not surprising that there is a lack of this kind of dataset, as collecting an appropriate amount of child speech involves many difficulties [6]. Typically, children are unable to articulate all speech units present in the language, they have limited reading skills and short attention spans. These issues result in irregular speech styles and imperfect recording samples [7].

The My Science Tutor MyST Dataset [8] can be considered the largest-scale available child speech corpus for research purposes. The dataset includes 393 hours of conversational child speech, with a total of 228,874 utterances. Approximately, 197 hours of the dataset were transcribed. On the other hand, MyST comes with many problems, such as utterances without any phonetic meaning, noisy background. Moreover, there is poor audio quality, characterized by children speaking very close to the microphone. Through manual examination, some transcriptions were allocated to incorrect audio samples completely. As an illustration, within the supplied transcription, there was the sentence, "No, I don't hearing even a candle burns". Yet, in the actual transcription, it reads, "No, I don't hear anything when the candle burns".

In the domain of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems, it has been observed that even the robust models trained on adult data exhibit suboptimal performance when applied to child voices. This is attributed to the inherent differences between adult and child speech. Besides less developed speech production and perception models they have higher fundamental frequency, and shorter vocal tract length [9].

To bridge the performance gap in ASR models between adults and children, several well-known child datasets such as CMU Kids dataset [10], OGI Kids' Speech Corpus [11], Tball corpus [12], Providence Corpus [13] were used for training and testing ASR systems. However, Child ASR remains a challenging task due to various issues associated with these datasets. These issues include the absence of correct labels, instances of children not vocalizing, audio containing noise, difficulties in accessing the dataset [14].

To improve the performance of ASR and expressive speech synthesis models, we need to use high-quality child datasets for training or adapt the existing acoustic models. To this end, we propose the ChildTinyTalks (CTT) dataset. CTT stands as an expressive child dataset, encompassing 2 hours of speech gathered from 25 students in grades spanning from third to fourth grade. These students engage in storytelling and recounting their experiences. The new dataset containing 1200 audio samples has been transcribed at the word level, comprising 4 classes of voice expressions. The source of the dataset is TEDxKid recordings [15].

Our paper is organized in the following way. In Section 2, we provide an overview of existing child datasets and popular techniques to address the problem of child dataset scarcity. Section 3 highlight our data collection and labelling. In this chapter, we also give a description and present key statistics of our dataset. Section 4 includes our baseline AutoVocoder speech synthesis model and a comparative study between the performance of the AutoVocoder trained on both our CTT dataset and the large-scale LJ Speech dataset [16]. In Section 5, we give the accuracy metrics and report the results of training our baseline model using both datasets across both objective and subjective testing benchmarks. Finally, Section 6 sums up our conclusions.

2 Related Work

The most attractive datasets for training child TTS and ASR models are: MyST, CMU Kids dataset [10], OGI Kids' Speech Corpus [11], Tball corpus [12], and Providence

Corpus [13]. However, each of them comes with its own set of limitations. For instance, they lack expressive styles, which are crucial for training expressive child TTS models. Moreover, the absence of explicit correctness labels, audio samples without transcriptions and noisy data.

To fill this gap, many studies have aimed to tackle these challenges by adapting the acoustic features of child speech to align with those of models trained on adult speech [17]. Most of them used transfer learning approaches from adult to child speech and found it to be very helpful [18], [19], [20]. Maximum Likelihood Linear Regression (MLLR) [21], and stochastic feature mapping (SFM) [22] have been employed as adaptation methods, proving beneficial for adapting to child speech. The trend indicated that as the age of the child speaker increased, there was a reduced need for data adaptation. Consequently, younger children encountered more mismatch with adult speech. Other efforts have attempted data augmentation setups to increase training data by adding child speech. In general, this has not proven fruitful [23], [24].

For expressive child speech, a few studies have focused on exploring emotions in children's stories [25], [26]. To address the limited availability of child datasets, we introduce the CTT dataset. It has been transcribed at the word level, comprising four classes of expressive styles: sadness, excitement, happiness, and neutral.

3 ChildTinyTalks (CTT)

3.1 Description

The main idea of crawling speakers on YouTube was inspired by [27], [28]. They exclusively utilize YouTube as their primary source of data. CTT includes over 1200 utterances from 25 speakers extracted from TEDx Talks for Kids events uploaded to YouTube. We formulated a hypothesis suggesting that there are several YouTube channels, featuring children speaking. Typically, these channels are visually distinguishable, either by examining a grid of video previews or automatically through clustering sequences of audio speaker embeddings from videos. Based on this idea, we focused on TEDx Talks for Kids events, as this channel offers high-quality content recorded in a silent environment. Additionally, the speakers range in age from 6 to 11 years.

The key statistics of our dataset are described in Table 1. The gender distribution for CTT dataset is 52% and 48% for boys and girls respectively.

Table 1: ChildTinyTalk CTT Description

Dataset	Statistics
Number of POI	25
Number of Utterances	1200
Number of hours	2
Number of filtered Videos	100
Number of videos per POI	3
Avg Number of utterances per POI	48
Avg length of utterances [s]	6.71

The language is only American English. The percentage of styles is 30% sad, 35% excited, 15% happiness and 20% neutral. Ten children from 6 to 7 years, fifteen children from 8 to 11 years. We intend to make CTT publicly available, but it requires agreements with the TEDx for Kids copyright holder, which are currently in progress.

3.2 Data collecting and filtering

The TEDx YouTube channel has been processed and filtered based on the number of available child videos, focusing on ages ranging from 6 to 11 years old. Audio was extracted from all TEDx for Kids videos that passed filtration phase.

3.3 Expressive styles in ChildTinyTalks

CTT is a high-quality expressive speech dataset that includes both expressively rendered and presenting speech. The dataset covers four classes of expressive styles (sadness, excitement, happiness, and neutral), so it can be used to build expressive child synthesis models. These four speaking styles are uttered by girls and boys in the English language. We offer illustrative audio samples from the CTT dataset and showcase v0-coded samples achieved by baseline models are available online¹.

¹ <https://github.com/shaimaalwaisi/ChildTinyTalks-CTT-dataset>

Table 2: Examples of captions in ChildTinyTalk CTT

Style	Caption
Sadness	No one would invite him to their birthdays or include him in their group of friends it made both me and Ben really sad
Excitement	I feel good knowing I can do something for others to make them feel happy
Neutral	Number one think on the positives like I did in my room
Happiness	You're right it was amazing I even got, to do a campaign for red nose day it's, where everyone comes together to get rid of child poverty

3.4 Data preprocessing

All audio files were decoded to and downsampled to mono wav format (sampling rate: 22.05 kHz, 16 bit PCM quantization) commonly used for speech and voice recognition tasks. We performed downsampling of the source signals of the audio channel of MP4 44.1 kHz in FLAC encoding. We entirely omitted any visual information from the TEDx channel. Sometimes, the audio files may contain substantial periods of silence, we removed all such silence regions, leaving only a small fraction at the beginning and end of the audio samples roughly 4 seconds. Audio samples with a significant amount of noise or crosstalk were removed with the help of Praat software [29]. The samples have been transcribed at the word level. We corrected obvious spelling errors in the transcriptions. We attempted to preserve explicitly mispronounced words to the greatest extent possible.

To ensure consistent Mel-spectrograms later in the training process, the lengths of audio signals are normalized to averaging 5.5 seconds. To address scenarios where the audio signal is shorter than the desired segment size, it is padded with zeros to match the specified segment size. This guarantees uniform lengths for all audio signals presented to the neural model.

4 Experiments

To demonstrate the efficiency of CTT in real-world situations, AutoVocoder models were trained and used for test waveform generation [30]. The baseline AutoVocoder [30] model was trained on both the LJ speech dataset and our CTT dataset. AutoVocoder is a voice encoder designed for training on speech waveforms with low computational cost. We chose AutoVocoder due to its state-of-the-art capabilities in speech synthesis. It has demonstrated outstanding results, particularly in fine-tuning for child

speech [31]. The configuration of the AutoVocoder involved Adam optimizer, a Batch Size of 16, and Learning Rate set at 0.0002. Training was conducted on a server running Ubuntu 16.04.7 LTS, with NVIDIA-SMI and CUDA version 11.4 for efficient utilization of GPU type NVIDIA TITAN Xp. The audio samples in the dataset have been split into 80% for the training set and 20% for the testing set. The training set was used to train the AutoVocoder on the features of both groups of children, The validation set from both age groups was used to evaluate and fine-tune the model's performance during training.

Fig. 1. Example of melSpectrogram and F0 comparison between reference and child audio synthesized for a boy and a girl : (a) ground truth spectrogram and F0, (b) CTT_AutoVocoder spectrogram and F0 Trained on our dataset CTT, and (c) LJSpeech_AutoVocoder spectrogram and F0 trained on LJ speech 1.1 dataset. The horizontal axis gives the time dimension for the audio, while the left vertical axis represents the frequency dimensions. The right vertical axis represents the fundamental frequency

4.1 Objective test

Mel-Cepstral Distortion MCD (dB): We utilized the mel-cepstral distortion (MCD) [32] as a distance metric to objectively evaluate the overall synthesized sound quality. It is commonly used to quantify the difference between two time-aligned mel-cepstral

sequences. MCD is a common measure employed to quantify the dissimilarity between two time-aligned mel-cepstral sequences. For both models, we conducted an average MCD calculation across twelve synthesized sound samples, encompassing both girls and boys. The samples synthesized by AutoVocoder trained on the CTT dataset and the corresponding ground-truth samples, as shown in Table II. The synthesized speech generated by the AutoVocoder closely aligns with the characteristics of the ground-truth reference speech. MCD values are calculated based on the following equation:

$$\text{MCD} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^D (y_{i,j} - \hat{y}_{i,j})^2} \quad (1)$$

Where \hat{y}_i represents the i^{th} coefficient of the generated MCCs, while y_i denotes the i^{th} coefficient of the ground truth MCCs.

The smaller the MCD between the synthesized and original mel-cepstral sequences, the higher the similarity between the synthesized and original speech. CTT_AutoVocoder, trained on the CTT dataset, exhibited comparable results to the LJ_AutoVocoder, trained on 24 hours of adult sound data. The model trained on CTT achieved an MCD value of 1.84 for girl audio samples. For boy audio samples, the MCD value for CTT_AutoVocoder was 2.05. For LJ_AutoVocoder, the MCD values across all speakers were 1.97 for boys and 2.13 for girls.

Table 3: Mel-cepstral distortions mcd (db) average results between the transformed and original mel cepstral sequences for 12 samples produced during the experiments by both models.

Systems	Boy	Girl
CTT_AutoVocoder	2.05	1.84
LJSpeech_AutoVocoder	1.97	2.13

F0 root mean square error (F0-RMSE): In comparing log F0 values between the ground truth and synthesized waveform, we utilized F0 root mean square error (F0-RMSE) [33] as an evaluation metric. The F0-RMSE values for each model across 12 samples are reported in Table 3. The F0-RMSE is computed using the following equation:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (F0_i - \hat{F}0_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

In the above equation, N represent the total number of frames in the speech, the term $\hat{F}0_i$ denotes the fundamental frequency F0 at the i^{th} frame of the generated waveform, and $F0_i$ represents the F0 value at the i^{th} frame of the ground truth. waveform. The smaller value of F0-RMSE implies a lower prediction error. In our evaluation, we calculated RMSE values by comparing the ground truth waveform's fundamental frequency (F0) with the synthesized waveform's.

Table 4: F0 Root Mean Square Error (F0-RMSE): values for both models as an average over 12 samples for both genders.

Systems	Boy	Girl
CTT_AutoVocoder	2.96	3.23
LJSpeech_AutoVocoder	3.00	3.19

It was observed that both models exhibited convergent results in terms of F0-RMSE. Across all evaluated metrics, the AutoVocoder trained on the CTT Dataset demonstrated exceptional performance in synthesizing highly quality sounds. It exhibited a remarkable ability to closely approximate the quality of the original sound.

4.2 Subjective listening test

A MUSHRA (Multiple Stimuli with Hidden Reference and Anchor) style evaluation [34] was used to compare the performance of AutoVocoder trained on both the CTT and LJSpeech Datasets. Each MUSHRA screen presented 4 stimuli to the listener for evaluation. These were CTT_AutoVocoder, LJSpeech_AutoVocoder, lower-anchor: low-pass filtered at 3.5 kHz, and ground truth. Twelve unseen samples during the training phase are used in the listening test. Twenty three listeners were instructed to evaluate and rate the stimuli based on the provided conditions. Listeners were instructed to find the ground truth within those 4 samples and assign it a score ranging from (highly not similar, not similar, intermediate similar and highly similar), whilst rating all samples. Fig. 2 shows the mean naturalness scores for the models.

Fig 2. The MUSHRA scores for the Mean naturalness are presented for (a) Ground truth (b) CTT_ AutoVocoder (c) LJSpeech_ AutoVocoder (d) Lower anchor, with the average results shown. A higher value indicates better overall quality.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the MUSHRA test results demonstrate a comparable preference among listeners for the synthesized sound samples produced by both AutoVocoders

across genders. Specifically, there is a similar preference for the audio samples generated by the CTT_AutoVocoder and LJSpeech_AutoVocoder. The preferences of listeners indicated that the CTT_AutoVocoder exhibited a significant similarity to the ground truth in the MUSHRA test results. Notably, 76% of respondents perceived the CTT_AutoVocoder as very similar to the ground truth audio samples.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we introduced a new expressive CTT dataset for child speech synthesis and TTS applications. CTT includes over 1200 utterances from 25 children extracted from TEDx Talks for Kids events uploaded to YouTube. The age varies from 6 to 11 years. To verify the effectiveness of CTT in real-world situations, AutoVocoder models were trained and synthesized samples were generated. The models were trained on both LJSpeech large scale dataset and our CTT dataset. The experimental results indicate that the CTT dataset can steadily give comparable results with acoustic model trained on a large-scale dataset with a size of less than 10% of the large dataset.

Additionally, the dataset introduced here has the potential to be used for ASR systems that often struggle with child speech.

The limitations of our dataset are its ~~relatively~~ small size, and the fact that it is not publicly available yet. However, the dataset is accessible for research purposes. We hope that our new dataset will be adopted, alongside other child datasets as a benchmark in the speech processing research community to train models for child speech. In future work, we can further augment the dataset through augmentation techniques, employing it in the development of fully expressive child text to speech synthesis and enhance the duration by increasing the number of hours.

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